

Preparation of Production Stage Process Maps in Satellite Enterprises

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ABSTRACT

This research seeks to analyze the procedures involved in the manufacturing stages of satellites. The satellite production phase, applicable to both communication satellites and other artificial satellites, encompasses the specification of requirements, as well as the procedures of manufacture, assembly, integration, and testing after the design phase. The manufacturing phase is crucial for a satellite firm to ensure that its satellites function optimally throughout their intended lifespan in orbit and successfully fulfill their missions. To guarantee the precision of the design and manufacturing procedures appropriate for space conditions, the satellite undergoes a series of specialized tests at testing facilities from the production site to the launch location. The equipment appropriate for space conditions intended for satellite usage is chosen during the design process. The relevant equipment and the manufactured satellite must undergo the requisite testing.

Keywords: *Satellite, Process Mapping, Testing, Orbit Types, Production Phase*

INTRODUCTION

Communication is an essential need for mankind now, just as it was in the past. The technical advancements of the previous century, along with the extensive communications services enabled by satellite communication systems, have been tailored to fulfill human requirements. A new world has evolved in which individuals may effortlessly converse and acquire information with greater ease. The advancement of technology results in the variety of communication networks and an expansion of available services. In the contemporary world, the need for satellites has escalated to provide uninterrupted and rapid communication among people and communities. Currently, technologically sophisticated nations are significantly investing in satellite technologies, seen as the only catalyst for a swift transition to an information society.

The term satellite mostly evokes thoughts of communication. Satellites are used in several domains, including terrestrial event study, observation, astronomical monitoring, and meteorological forecasting.

A government seeking to avoid dependence on other nations must advance in space exploration and satellite technology. This can only be accomplished via local and national production in this sector, together with the provision of requisite economic and political support to enterprises.

The first phase of satellite production involves the creation of a manufacturing facility equipped with specialized technological apparatus to fulfill the demands of a study including highly sensitive production and testing processes related to satellite technology. This research has thoroughly investigated the manufacture, assembly, integration, and testing procedures of satellites based on prior experiences. The manufacturing process starts with feasibility and design, followed by assembly, integration, and testing. Throughout the satellite manufacturing process, many tests are conducted after the integration of subsystem equipment. Upon completion of satellite manufacture and testing, it is transferred to the launch site for preparatory tests prior to space flight.

AIM

This study will detail the knowledge and experience acquired through individual application and research concerning the verification of all satellite subsystems from the design phase through production and testing, culminating in their deployment in orbit for operational longevity, as well as the facilities and activities conducted within a satellite production center. The research aims to delineate the phases and procedures that satellites undergo during manufacture, traversing different orbits outside the atmosphere at certain distances from the Earth.

CONCEPTUAL DIMENSION OF THE STUDY

A satellite is described as a tiny, artificial object launched from Earth into space and positioned at certain distances for purposes such as communication, scientific research, military applications, meteorology, or other objectives. All satellites are positioned in orbits known as elliptical or circular trajectories at varying distances from the Earth. Satellite orbits, categorized by their proximity to the Earth's center and their respective locations, are analyzed in three segments: Near Earth Orbit, Medium Earth Orbit, and Geostationary Orbit. Near Earth Orbit; satellites in this region are positioned in orbit at altitudes ranging from 160 km to 2000 km above the Earth. Medium Earth Orbit; spacecraft in this orbit traverse distances ranging from 2000 km to 36000 km from the Earth.

Geostationary Orbit; spacecraft in this orbit are situated inside the Clark Belt, roughly 36,000 km from the Earth's core. This orbit is characterized as one that travels in synchrony with the Earth.

The significant orbit types used in artificial satellites are shown in Figure 1 below:

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Figure 1. Orbit Types

The basis of space studies is the three-item law discovered by Kepler, which governs the motions of the planets around the sun and is given below (Berlin, 2010).

1. Each planet moves in elliptical orbits with the Sun at one of its foci.
2. As the planets move in their orbits, they sweep out equal areas in equal periods of time.
3. The square of the time it takes for a planet to complete one revolution in its orbit is proportional to the cube of the length of the major semi-axis of the ellipse.

The implications of these rules for satellites are as follows: Kepler's law states that all planets revolve around the Sun. All satellites similarly traverse several sorts of orbits around the Earth. The distance of a satellite from the Earth correlates with its velocity. Theoretically, a satellite's orbit will stay stable if the equilibrium between gravitational and centripetal forces is maintained.

For a satellite in orbit above the Earth to be directed to a specific location on the Earth's surface and to ensure continuous communication, synchronization between the satellite and the Earth is essential.

The concept of worldwide communication via satellites was first proposed by British physicist and science fiction author Arthur C. Clarke in May 1945. In his article "Extra-Terrestrial Relays" published in "Wireless World," Clarke proposed that a satellite positioned at an altitude of 36,000 km in Geosynchronous Orbit would complete a revolution every 24 hours, appearing stationary from the ground. He further asserted that three satellites positioned 120 degrees apart could facilitate global radio communication (Clarke, 1945). Subsequent to Clarke's publication, research began to implement this concept, which might provide significant prospects in the realm of communication, into practical applications. The first research, demonstrating the rapid advancement of satellite communication systems, began in 1957 with the Soviet Union's launch of the SPUTNIK-1 satellite into orbit. In 1960, the United States (NASA) launched ECHO-1, a balloon-shaped satellite that functioned in a circular orbit at an altitude of 1600 km, encased in metallic layers. (Garg & Wilkes, 1996).

PROCESS AND PROCESS MAPPING

Scientific and technical advancements have expedited globalization by effectively compressing the globe, facilitating the exchange of information across nations, introducing new technologies and innovations, and enhancing public awareness. Although communication has transcended national boundaries, it has concurrently contracted the globe.

The objective of founding a firm is to ensure its longevity. Similar to other corporations, satellite manufacturing enterprises must monitor emerging advancements to endure and remain aligned with swiftly evolving technology. Businesses must adapt their always developing management, comprehension, practices, and methodologies. Not every company must undergo a challenging and developmental transition process. Nevertheless, those that begin this process will have the opportunity to sustain their achievement in the future. Furthermore, such firms

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exhibit heightened sensitivity to their clientele and strive to save expenses by enhancing quality and performance.

Businesses are compelled to continually evolve due to factors such as globalization, rapid advancements in information technology, competition, and both external and internal political developments. Internal challenges include insufficient buyer demand, rising buyer dissatisfaction, shifts in objectives, and declines in performance metrics. Consequently, companies must use resources with more effectiveness and efficiency. This may be accomplished via the comprehensive implementation of procedures and process management. Multiple inputs must undergo a systematic procedure to provide the final result. A process comprises a sequence of operations that enhance inputs to get a certain outcome.

Another definition posits that a process encompasses processes designed to provide value for the customer via inputs, resulting in value-added outputs derived from these inputs (Nezihi, 2015). The connected inputs are often classified into five primary categories: personnel, equipment, materials, processes, and the environment (Öztürk, 2010). A process is described as an action or a connected series of activities that turn one or more inputs into one or more outputs, generating solutions for customers both inside and outside the business.

Process management encompasses a sequence of operations designed to guarantee ongoing oversight and enhancement of processes. This management constitutes a cycle including continuous review, analysis, and development phases to guarantee the design, maintenance, and enhanced fulfillment of customer process requirements. Process management is an alternative management philosophy. It primarily emphasizes the definition of labor and processes in their whole (Tokcan, 2011).

The manufacture and testing phases of satellites are inherently complex and rigorous operations. The knowledge acquired from these procedures is crucial for ensuring performance and dependability.

Developing process maps is crucial for good management and organizational strategy in a corporation. It facilitates the identification and prevention of potential faults in the final result inside a certain system. Similar to other enterprises, satellite firms use technologies that include

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essential interrelated visual phases, such as process and process mapping, to enhance their efficiency and optimize their production processes.

The fundamental aspect of process management is identifying the services and products, including intermediary offerings, generated inside the company, and constructing a map of interrelated activities (process maps) necessary for their production (Özkan, 2009). Process maps, or process flow diagrams, are designed to explicitly illustrate the priority of actions conducted inside the process and the interrelations among these activities. As the activities sequentially progress in a certain sequence, these diagrams are referred to as flow charts. Process maps are meticulously crafted for each procedural step inside the activity's framework.

In process improvement studies, it is crucial to identify which activities would be impacted by modifications to the process activities.

The primary function of these maps is to graphically and progressively illustrate the links between processes. The maps illustrate which processes function as suppliers and which processes serve as suppliers themselves.

Process mapping is essential in satellite production to assess the precision of performance ratings for each stage of the final product, identify defects and issues that diminish or impede quality, and evaluate how both positive and negative activities contribute to the overall outcome.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The design, manufacture, and launch phases of satellites are intricate and delicate procedures. These procedures need effective management. Process management and process mapping enhance comprehension, oversight, enhancement, and the seamless advancement of complex processes.

The design of all satellites is intimately linked to the subsystems that comprise them and their attributes. Satellites generally have two fundamental portions and their respective subsystems. These originate from Ariespace, 2004.

1. Payload,

2. Satellite Platform and Subsystems,

- Orientation Control Subsystem
- Electrical Power Subsystem
- Telemetry, Telecommand, Distance Measurement Subsystem
- Propulsion Subsystem
- Thermal Control Subsystem
- Data Management Subsystem
- Structural Subsystem

The subsystems and components generally found in satellites are shown in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Satellite Components

The primary hazard to a satellite is the space environment in which it operates. When determining a satellite design, it is essential to pick materials and equipment that are appropriate for the area and exhibit enhanced durability. Before producing a satellite, it is essential to

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ascertain its intended function. The materials must be picked appropriately. All satellites undergo extensive performance and environmental mechanical testing to guarantee the precision of assembly and integration processes and to validate their resilience to environmental impacts during launch and in orbit. This system, incurring daily expenses of millions of liras, requires effective management processes. The process in satellite development starts with the customer's requirements and proceeds with the manufacturer's first analyses. Companies advance to the design phase by acquiring inputs like the satellite's purpose, mass, coverage area, and orbital parameters. The satellite, whose precision is guaranteed, undergoes the assembly, integration, and testing phases, culminating in the acceptance stage. A two-phase design methodology is implemented. The first phase is the preliminary design review, followed by the critical design review. The phases conclude with the finalization of the subsystem and equipment preliminary design, as well as the comprehensive study of the satellite's detailed system design (ECSS-M-ST-10C, 2008).

Process mapping delineates each phase of the satellite manufacturing process in detail, enhancing the comprehensibility of all phases and associated components. The procedures for mapping the satellite manufacturing phase operations are shown in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3. Satellite Production Stage Process Map

Satellite Integration and Test Systems

To execute these first satellite testing phases, the requisite test systems and equipment must be installed and provided to the manufacturing facility. The systems are enumerated as follows (TUSAŞ, 2024).

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- Thermal Vacuum Chamber
- EMC/EMI Laboratory
- Acoustic Test Room
- Mechanical Laboratories
- Integration room (100000 class)
- Vibration Test Facility
- Physical Properties Measurement System
- Compact Antenna Test Room
- Mechanical Ground Support Equipment
- Electrical Ground Support Equipment

Figure 4 below shows the image and test system area of the Space Systems Integration and Test Center, which is located in our country and is used as a production center for all satellites:

Figure 4. Space Systems Integration and Test Center (TUSAŞ, 2024).

Satellite Tests

Satellites undergo several tests to evaluate their resilience against potential adverse conditions throughout both the launch and operational phases after design and manufacture. These tests are scenarios constructed using actual values. Planning the tests, positioning the requisite testing apparatus, conducting the tests, and analyzing the findings are critical phases for the well-being of satellite manufacturing operations. A significant effort is dedicated to this phase, which is crucial in satellite manufacturing.

These tests are listed below:

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- Functional Tests
- Thermal Vacuum Tests
- Vibration and Shock Test
- Acoustic Testing
- Solar Panels Opening Tests
- Measurement of Physical Properties
- Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) / Electromagnetic Interference Tests (EMI)
- Antenna Tests
- Propulsion Subsystem Tests
- Pre-Launch Tests

The tests generally followed and implemented by satellite companies are given in Figure 5 below:

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Figure 5. Tests Applied to Satellites

ARGUMENT

This section will address the issues, drawbacks, and necessary remedies. No software programming is available for emergency usage to determine the distance and speed of satellites for transfer and orbital operations. This has shown to be essential, particularly during the launch phase.

Satellite operators are required to conduct X-ray imaging on components like propulsion subsystems, pipe welds, and the Optical Solar Reflector, which is situated on the outside surfaces of satellites, particularly during the manufacture and assembly stages. The processes of gasoline filling and testing are hazardous; hence, actual fuel is not used. Instead, simulated fluids, such as gas or water, are used to meet the weight criteria. During the

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filling process, the quantity of filters used must be augmented to avert micron-level pollution from infiltrating the gasoline.

Contemporary satellite enterprises must do essential research on occupational health to ensure their corporate sustainability and enhance productivity and quality. Establishing a healthy and safe working environment requires multidisciplinary and intricate approaches. It is essential to assess all circumstances, including lighting, ventilation, noise, temperature, and humidity in the workplace, and to implement appropriate steps to ensure that personnel operate in an ergonomically sound and safe setting.

The physical parameters of satellites, which traverse three axes in their orbits, such as center of gravity and inertia, must be measured with precision. To guarantee the compatibility of the relevant parameters, these tests should be conducted mostly at night when the work area is sparsely populated.

Thermal Vacuum Tests, which replicate the orbital environment including pressure, temperature, and solar radiation, used thermal rods. A test system with big lights that simulate sunlight is necessary to conduct more sensitive testing appropriate for space settings. A two-axis shaker, a device that generates vibrations, is often used for vibration testing to assess the endurance of satellites under anticipated vibrational stresses. For further axis testing, the satellite must be detached from the adapter and then reattached. This poses a danger to the satellite's health. A three-axis shaker that is constructed in a single operation must be used for this purpose.

In the Shock and Separation test, the rubber material situated at the base of the launch adapter must adhere to space conditions and requirements to prevent it from detaching and sustaining damage.

Acoustic tests are conducted to replicate the intense noise generated during launch and to assess the satellite's ability to endure significant stress. Businesses use nitrogen gas due of its economical nature. For optimal cost-effectiveness and efficacy, such testing should be conducted using dry air.

Spacecraft and satellites must use solar panels to harness all the electrical energy required from the Sun. Solar Panel Opening Tests are conducted to verify the panels' compatibility with the

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spacecraft and the space environment. Solar Panel Opening Tests and Flash Explosion Tests are conducted to evaluate the deployment of the sealed panels attached to the satellite structure. It is essential to ascertain that the safety pyro valves used for releasing the connection mechanisms function properly in conjunction with both the primary and spare components. These must be immediately opened using the pyro valve at least once in the space environment to ensure the satellite's health.

CONCLUSION

The subsequent phase of a satellite after the construction stage is its launch into orbit. Once the satellite is launched into orbit, no physical action from the ground can rectify any technical problem that may arise. Consequently, precautions must be made to guarantee that the manufacturing phase aligns with spatial environmental conditions. For satellites to effectively perform their functions in orbit over an extended period, impeccable design, along with a faultless manufacturing and testing procedure, is essential.

The research provides information on the assembly, integration, and testing processes, including the manufacturing procedures for satellites and the equipment used during this phase, as well as the tests conducted. Moreover, insights and experiences acquired via individual application and research related to activities such as manufacturing and testing phases in satellites are communicated.

The manufacturing process is a rigorous and exhausting phase that starts with the satellite's design and concludes with its deployment into orbit. Satellites that successfully complete this process must pass the assembly, integration, and testing phases, which are critical to ensuring protection from environmental effects encountered during their operational lifespan and to maintain their mission in orbit effectively.

The critical components in this method are the proficient and seasoned expert staff and the exceptionally high manufacturing charges. The actions in the manufacturing process that significantly contribute to minimizing satellite production costs must be well handled. The creation of this manufacturing facility for the first time in our country, together with the training

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of its staff, represents significant advancements in terms of cost efficiency and national and local production.

Consequently, all research and development activities necessary for significant projects, which may encompass technological assessments of satellites, including communication and observation satellites, as well as earthquake monitoring, environmental studies, meteorological analysis, remote sensing, scientific experimentation, and imaging of natural resources, must receive support.

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